

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Anontatsion. Metaphor is an effective way of forming medical terms. Metaphors are also very useful in creating medical terms. In the article, the medical terms formed on the basis of metaphor are grouped based on their dictionary meanings.

Key words: communication, language, medical terms, metaphor, means of communication in medicine, human body parts.

Terms appear in the language on the basis of universal laws (derivation, semantic migration, metonymization) and others. In the formation and development of the terminology of the Uzbek language, it is possible to observe the formation of many medical terms through metaphor. Usually, a term (from the Latin "terminus" - "limit", "boundary mark") is a word or combination of words that clearly expresses the concept of something related to science, technology and other fields, the scope of use of which is limited to these fields. Terms differ from common words in terms such as being unambiguous, lacking in expressiveness and emotionality. As in all lexical resources of the Uzbek language, the terms have their own ways of enrichment and they correspond to the general laws of the development of our language. There is not a single language in the world that has not acquired foreign words. In order to express a new concept in all languages, either a ready-made term from another language is adopted, or a word or term existing in this language is used, or a new term is created. Including, the medical terminology that we are going to talk about has also passed its great development path. According to terminologists, metaphor plays the main role in the formation of a term in the semantic method. In this case, such new terms are created due to the fact that they are similar in form and color of the words of common literary or living language. In many works dedicated to the study of the terminological systems of various fields of the Uzbek language, term formation using the semantic method is recognized as an important source of terminology enrichment. However, when researching medical terms, the terms in which the metaphor is considered the main tool appeared mainly by the semantic-syntactic method. It is known that in the enrichment of medical terminology, which began to be formed from very ancient

times, the formation of terms in a semantic way has been used. By the beginning of the 20th century, with the formation and rapid development of cognitive linguistics, it was recognized that metaphor is a multifaceted, extremely complex phenomenon, and its essence as a manifestation of fundamental cognitive activity was revealed. Metaphor is an effective way of forming medical terms. Metaphors are also very useful in creating medical terms. Medicinally, scurvy, tympanic membrane, cornea, black eye, chicken pox, small pox, tetanus, eyeball, fish coin, earlobe, nasopharyngeal conch, auricular conch, the use of terms such as urethra is directly related to the metaphor. Modern medical terminology is one of the most complex in the system of terms. It contains thousands of words and phrases. One of the most productive ways to create a term is metaphor. Metaphor is one of the main methods of pictorial representation of reality and reflects a certain linguistic image of the world in terminology. The universal feature of a metaphor is that it exists in the mind of any person, regardless of what language they speak. Medical terminology is one of the unique layers of word combinations that differ from ordinary words by their structural, semantic, word-forming and stylistic features, and thus have a special place in the lexical system of the language. Medical terms created on the basis of metaphor can be divided as follows.

1. Metaphorical medical terms created in relation to humans. In this case, the terms are based on similarities, such as human biological characteristics (death, sleep, vision): cecum, dead pulp, dead cell. The caecum is the beginning of the large intestine in humans and mammals, located in the right iliac fossa, and at the junction with the ileum, it has semicircular folds and a cover. If we pay attention to the term, it is called by this name because one side of it is closed. Also, the anthropomorphic metaphor can include the names of historical figures, literary heroes, fairy tales, legends: Voltaire's face, Achilles heel, "Alice in Wonderland" syndrome, Oedipus complex. In medicine, the names of body parts are used metaphorically as the names of other organs, and the following terms, such as ventricle, leg, head, head, lip, waist, tongue, are also used in compound form. Such terms as head of the bone, girdle of the kidney, ventricle of the heart, blood corpuscle, cervix, posterior belly of the muscle, duodenum, palatine lobe, cerebral peduncle, quadriceps muscle, triceps muscle are vivid examples of this.
2. Terms referring to clothing and their parts: brain top, brain seam, hearing border, belly fold, shoulder girdle.
3. Household items used in everyday life, names of various objects participated in the formation of the term metaphorically: bladder, gall bladder, brain stem, ear gum, liver

node, nog Diaphragm, cornea, dome of the skull, bony layer, calculus, retinal cups, umbilical system, renal pelvis, mastoid fibers, nerve fiber, tympanic membrane, kidney ball, abdominal cavity, ear such as mirror, dandruff, foci of disease, chest, intestinal suction, kidney cup, rosary grain syndrome.

4. Botanical objects and the terms referring to them. In the medical terminology of the Uzbek language, a number of terms representing botanical objects are also used. In this place, the names of two different objects have arisen as such terms: 1) some plant names appear as medical terms: hair bulb, brain sprout, taste buds; 2) stages of plant development, the names of several parts in their structure: taste buds, cerebral cortex, bronchial tree, pharyngeal lobe, tonsil gland, adrenal gland cortex, cortical cell, like a flower.

5. Names of horse harnesses: Turkish saddle, lab yugancha, uzanchi.

6. Zoomorphic metaphors combine the names of animals, their body parts, and other names associated with their existence: brainworm, tiger heart, tiger, horsetail, fish coin, chicken meat, chicken disease, rabbit, filoleg, Terms such as "small skin", "door-leg", "ass", "sheep-nosed" skin tuberculosis, baccha, sea horse, fish roe syndrome are used metaphorically as names of diseases and symptoms of diseases.

7. Metaphors related to color. Color plays an important role in treatment. The terms containing the word representing the color indicate a specific symptom, define it. Such terms help to clarify the disease. In medicine, color coding is one of the main diagnostic signs of diseases, symptoms, skin, etc. In the medical terminology of the Uzbek language, the following color terms can be found: crimson tongue, gray shell of the brain, black, red, yellow, yellow fever, yellow body, bluish, pink iron, black, targ il tana, scabies, black lameness, yellow spots.

8. Use of geographic terms as terms in medicine: ureter, vascular canal, optic canal, blood islet, islet of Langerhans, bone canal, chov canal, gastric canal, dental canal, femoral canal.

Metaphor is not limited to the realm of language, as human thought processes themselves are metaphors. Metaphor exists in the human conceptual system and is an effective way of forming medical terms. Metaphor nomenclature preserves the consistency inherent in terminology during its construction, and also brings their consistency to the terminology system, based on the conceptual conditioning of metaphor models and metaphors. Metaphor nominations help to acquire such qualities as general acceptance, convenience.

In our language, there are many cases where the names of diseases are called by Uzbek words. This shows that medical terminology is enriched with words with a national color. Among the medical terms, the presence of the names of diseases such as dust mites (allergy), smallpox, bilious rubella, dysentery, zotiljam, in general, the use of such terms in speech as an alternative to foreign names in the Uzbek language, at the same time, euphemization with the replacement of medical terms.

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